

DEVELOPMENT OF HIGHER EDUCATION SYSTEM THE PROSPECT OF THE CONCEPTION (USING SOFT SKILLS AS AN EXAMPLE)

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<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7939706>

Annotation: In this article, the priorities of the systematic reform of higher education in the Republic of Uzbekistan, raising the process of training highly qualified personnel with modern knowledge and high moral and ethical qualities to a new level in terms of quality, higher education. It is based on the fact that the modernization of education, the development of the social sphere and economic sectors based on advanced educational technologies consists in the formation of a set of knowledge and skills.

Key words: regulatory and legal, universal education, universal competencies, life adaptability, advanced educational technologies, moral and ethical, professional activity, international experiences, innovation.

Continuing education should be characterized by the formation of universal competencies in students in accordance with state educational standards. In this regard, there are several approaches to the interpretation of these competencies in modern literature. In the course of the gradual development of the normative and legal framework of the educational activity of the Republic of Uzbekistan, there is a unified complex of defined concepts. In this case, the national personnel training program represents the consistency of the formation and improvement of universal competencies from preschool education to further higher education, that is, from universal educational activities in a higher education institution. In particular, the concepts of "vital" and "adaptability" of soft skills are used. The purpose of the article is to determine the possibilities of using these concepts in continuous education.

Based on international experiences, the introduction of advanced standards of higher education, including the gradual transition from education focused on theoretical knowledge to the formation of practical skills in educational programs, higher raising the content of education to a new level in terms of quality, establishing a system of training highly qualified personnel who can contribute to the sustainable development of the social sphere and economic sectors, and who can find their place in the labor market, in the field of education. The policy of the state of Uzbekistan is closely related to the concept of development of the higher education system until 2030[1] in all types of education.

The relevance of this concept is explained by the fact that with the rapid growth of the digital economy, the need for continuous development of personnel and not only personnel with a set of skills focused on a narrow specialty, but also specialists with a wide range of universal competencies is in the existence of the need. Determining the priorities of the systematic reform of higher education in the Republic of Uzbekistan, raising the process of training highly qualified personnel with modern knowledge and high moral and ethical qualities to a new level in terms of quality, modernization of higher education, based on advanced educational technologies, in the development of the social sphere and economic sectors, it is explained by the acquisition of universal competences SOFT SKILLS, that is, life and flexibility skills. If life and adaptability skills are considered as important and basic knowledge and skills, it can be clearly seen that they allow a person to work successfully in his chosen

professional activity. Also, scientific works devoted to the formation of these skills further enrich local scientific and popular scientific publications. As a result of a random search of scientific articles of 2009-2019 on this topic, more than 46 scientific works of authors dealing with the formation of life skills were identified.

The idea of these articles is united within the framework of the principle of continuous education. As the main component of the national model of personnel training, continuous education is the basis of qualified competitive personnel training and includes all types of education, state educational standards, the structure of the personnel training system and its operating environment. In turn, the goal of the "National Personnel Training Program" is to radically reform the education sector, to free it from the ideological views and prejudices left over from the past, to provide high moral and ethical standards at the level of developed democratic countries. is to create a national system of training qualified personnel [2]. This proves that the above-mentioned Concept is a logical continuation of this program in its modern interpretation. For example, among the tasks of the program, the system and content of personnel training is aimed at restructuring based on the prospects of social and economic development of the country, the needs of society, and the modern achievements of science, culture, technique and technology.

However, today's existing traditional education system, i.e., educational programs, curricula, educational processes, and "future competencies" that are used in the continuous education system are not There is a gap between [2]. This increases the relevance of applying SOFT SKILLS to the continuous education system. Recommendations on soft-skills will help everyone to actively move forward in the perspective of developing the educational system. It is necessary to take into account the following general rules:

Development should be made a continuous process. In turn, it is necessary to have experience, to be able to solve complex tasks, to act better than in a simple way. The main thing is not to stop.

1. Learning to plan the stages of development competently;
2. Use of different forms;
3. To show curiosity, to study the happenings around.
4. It is very important to choose directions that will be of real importance in your work.
5. Forming the habit of reading more is a great solution.

Therefore, the planned start of each work helps to eliminate the negative consequences of this work in time, and most importantly, to successfully complete the work. In turn, an individual plan for the formation of soft skills can be developed at any convenient time, and the main thing is that a person should consciously take responsibility for his personal development.

In conclusion, it should be noted that the competencies of modern people living in the 21st century must meet the requirements of the transforming society and state economy. Thanks to them, flexible societies are created that can quickly meet the needs of people in complex socio-political and economic spheres. At the same time, if the "competencies of the future" are widely used by people, the transformation of society and economy will be built on a faster and more reliable basis.

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